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BUSINESS INCUBATORS FOR START –UP IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Many government programs contain policy instruments addressing SMEs. New structures and strategies are being explored that will help small enterprises to grow and provide a promising future in the global market. In a number of more competitive economies, business incubation is one of the tools that have helped to create and support new entrepreneurial skills and businesses. The aim of the study is to cover entire research about finding out about the working of an Indian Business Incubator and its programs if any. This study is based on secondary research to study the working of an innovative incubator in India. The study has been analyzed with the help of pie charts, bar graph and smart art. The study concluded that Business Incubators provide a higher level of support to start-ups and new entrepreneurs as compared to the other supports available. Business Incubation, as a process is multidimensional and can have different objectives as regards ideas, community, time and accessibility

INTRODUCTION

In today's global economy, small and medium scale enterprises are increasingly a force for enhancing national economic growth and employment. Many government programs contain policy instruments addressing SMEs. New structures and strategies are being explored that will help small enterprises to grow and provide a promising future in the global market. In a number of more competitive economies, business incubation is one of the tools that have helped to create and support new entrepreneurial skills and businesses. The incubation process and programs often called "New Entrepreneur Creation Projects" have included services for on the spot diagnosis and treatment of business problems, dramatically lowering the usual early stage failure rate. The business incubator target group includes small entrepreneurs that want to grow, new graduates and those who would like to develop their talent and ideas and commercialize them. An exercise aimed at finding out the innovative paths incubation has ventured into and to undertake a study on them, will give a deep

understanding of how incubation is the journey to quick evolution. As incubators are widely being accepted, to check their viability in the Indian market will help striking future growth oriented plans.

INCUBATOR MEANING

A business incubator as per corporate jargon is a company that helps new and start-up companies to develop. It is an organization designed to support the growth and usher the success of entrepreneurial companies through an array of business support resources and services that could include:

- Help with business basics
- Networking and Marketing assistance with links to strategic partners
- Market Research
- Help with accounting/financial management
- Access to bank loans, loan funds and guarantee programs
- Help with presentation skills and business etiquette
- Access to angel investors or venture capital
- Comprehensive business training programs and to higher education resources
- Advisory boards and mentors
- Technology commercialization assistance
- Help with regulatory compliance and Intellectual property management
- Physical Space

Any new startup must evaluate its need for an incubator and analyze its viability for their project.

Good sources for finding an incubator include state and local economic development departments and small business associations of respective countries.

Types

1. PUBLIC OR NOT-FOR-PROFIT INCUBATORS
2. PRIVATE INCUBATORS
3. ACADEMIC-RELATED INCUBATORS
4. PUBLIC/PRIVATE INCUBATORS

Incubation Procedure

Diagram displaying the steps in the process of Business Incubation

STARTUP INDIA

Startup India is a flagship initiative of the Government of India, intended to build a strong eco-system for nurturing innovation and start-ups in the country that will drive sustainable economic growth and generate large scale employment opportunities. With this Action Plan the Government hopes to accelerate spreading of the Startup movement from digital/ technology sector to other sectors including Agriculture, Manufacturing, Social Sector, Healthcare, Education etc.

Technology Incubation and Development Of Entrepreneurs (Tide)

Department of Electronics and Information Technology (DeitY) has implemented launched a scheme in 2008, as per the scheme provision, 27 centres are being supported at academic

institutions across India. TIDE has a multipronged approach in Electronics, ICT and Management. It assists institutions to strengthen their Technology Incubation Centres and enable young entrepreneurs to initiate technology start-up companies. The centres network with Angel Investors and Venture Capitalists who enable tenant companies to mature over a period of 2-3 years and ultimately graduate to a commercial place.

Virtual Start-Up Hub

An initiative by DEPARTMENT OF INDUSTRIAL POLICY AND PROMOTION (DIPP)

Developed by INVEST INDIA

Start-ups will have a LinkedIn-like platform to discover and interact with investors, mentors, incubators and other service providers in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. The new platform— an upgrade of Start-up India Hub will intelligently connect start-ups, based on the sector area, with investors and incubators. With features that will show up relevant government schemes and incentive Programme. Once a certain number of profiles are created, the portal will be integrated on Start-up India website and app.

NEED OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The need for the present study rose on account of the increasing number of startups that are growing and developing around us. In the field of commerce, startups are keenly read about, both at their finished and progressive stages. In the background of academia, business is studied in such depth that starting one's own business is a natural dream that commerce graduates seem to find the courage to usher.

The need for a project on relatively new and developing concepts like Business Incubators is necessary in order to begin our life in the actual world with awareness regarding the most upcoming arenas.

OBJECTIVES OF THE PRESENT STUDY

- To study the working of an innovative incubator in India.
- To evaluate the viability of business incubation in India.

SCOPE OF THE PRESENT STUDY

- Undertaking research on the working of an innovative incubator in India
- Checking the viability of incubators in India

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This secondary research is conducted in order to gain knowledge about the following:

1. Innovative incubation projects in India.
2. How an incubator can be a large outlet for innovation and welfare. Number of lives a socially inclined incubator can impact with job creation, better facilities in health and education, improvement of agricultural workings etc.
3. Parties involved in a successful and wide incubation process. Students, trainers, farmers, teachers, trustees, villagers etc.
4. How science is a binding force for the functions of an incubator, irrigation facilities' start-up for agriculture, 'save a mother', a health startup for proper nutrition of pregnant ladies and technological startups facilitating mobile laboratories for academia.

Methodology

This study is descriptive in nature based on the Annual Report of a business incubator. The study aims at finding out about the working of an Indian Business Incubator and its programs if any. This study is based on secondary research. The secondary data was collected from the Annual Report of Deshpande Foundation's Sandbox Ecosystem

Statistical Tools:

1. Bar Graph
2. Pie Chart
3. Smart art

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

1. Areas Covered By Sandbox

Fig. 1 Graph displaying the coverage of sectors done by Sandbox by percentage

The annual report of the Deshpande Foundation’s Sandbox explicitly talks about its partnerships in the various sectors. The highest as we can see is in the case of Livelihoods. The foundation claims to be improving livelihoods of more than 61,000 people. Up second is Education, where more than 12, 80,000 students are impacted, Chipper Sage, a for-profit company helping children with reading, is a partner, had ushered the opening of 15 government schools in the area. Coming third is Health where about 77,500 lives are positively impacted. OpASHA or Operation ASHA, a partner of Sandbox, specializes in last mile delivery of treatment for tuberculosis, in economically backward regions. Another partner, Save A Mother, works to reduce maternal mortality rates among low income communities. Fourth, we have the agriculture sector where 72,000 plus farmers are impacted. The Sandbox partnered with Manuvikasa to help harvest rainwater by constructing farm ponds for communities that faced acute water shortage. Another partner of Sandbox, BAIF created the Wadi concept of tree-based farming, to revitalize barren lands and generate income through horticulture and tree-based farming. And lastly there is technology where more than 20,000 people are claimed to be impacted.

2. THE STARTUP ARENA IN SANDBOX

Sandbox startups show the trend shown above with Rs. 50 crore revenue collections. If the business market is a whole then Sandbox has created jobs at the maximum, followed by idea

supporting for new ventures and giving them a push to enter the world of product making and selling.

Fig 2: Graph displaying the participation of Sandbox in the business market

Third up is incubation, the process as a whole, with funding, space provision, mentorship, training, marketing etc. Lastly there is seed funding where engaged ventures are only concerned with the initial funding.

3. THE LEAD PROJECT BY SANDBOX

Fig. 3: Diagram displaying the two forces of the Lead Program at Sandbox

LEAD is a project of the Sandbox built on a premise that education should not only impart technical skills for employability but also instill young individuals with a 'can do' attitude to put ideas into action. LEAD has pioneered a methodology that engages students with their

concerns for society to unleash leadership, and problem solving skills. Bullock cart brake system, smokeless chulha, portable mobile planetarium and portable metal cutting tool are some products created by Leaders under the Lead project.

FINDINGS

- **To study the working of an innovative incubator in India.**

Deshpande foundation's Sandbox Ecosystem is in unbeatable example of how business incubation can meet society. The incubator notes a three time increase in revenue from agricultural involvements. The Foundation's main motive is community development with a twist and Sandbox is a perfect example of its approach for entrepreneurship world.

- **To evaluate the viability of business incubation in India.**

We see a distinction between the various other forces that startups can be supported by, and how incubators provide a full proof plan to startups and parent them for two-three years. The second side to the viability will be the great talent hub our country holds and how performance of our government schemes, incubators and startups has been, in the little time that incubation got introduced.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

1. Business Incubators have found their niche in India with similar developmental approach schemes and visionary environment.
2. Business Incubation, as a process is multidimensional and can have different objectives as regards ideas, community, time and accessibility.
3. Business Incubators provide a higher level of support to start-ups and new entrepreneurs as compared to the other supports available.
4. The viability of incubators in India can be seen with the various sectors that have been positively impacted with incubation in India.
5. Business Incubation is not a limited concept fenced by the business market, rather interesting and useful merging of ideas can create long-term entrepreneurial as well as societal benefitting environment for new and old ventures.

6. Social responsibly does not necessarily have to be catered to by preparing for expenses and no expectation of revenue, a well-planned organisation can manage collection of revenue and goodwill together.

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